

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT 2014-15

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society

Address
Avenue Molière 128
1050 Ixelles Brussels

Contact
+32 (0)2 539 37 02
info@abis-global.org

Contents

About ABIS	3
Message from the President	4
Message from the Managing Director	5
13th ABIS Annual Colloquium 2014	6
ABIS Doctoral Summer School 2014	8
Knowledge Into Action Platform	10
Knowledge Into Action Forum 2015	12
EU-InnovatE	14
Alliance for Advancing Health Assets	16
Managing the Responsible Business Challenge in Africa	18
Innovation For Sustainability (I4S)	20
ABIS Thought Leadership Round Tables	22
EU Horizon 2020 Engagement Opportunities	24
ABIS Publications	26
ABIS Membership	28
Principles for Responsible Management Education (PRME)	31
ABIS Board of Directors	32
ABIS Team	33

About ABIS

About ABIS Global

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society is a global network of companies, academic institutions and affiliate members whose expertise, commitment and resources are leveraged to invest in a more sustainable future for business in society. ABIS enables informed decision-making on business in society issues through collaborative research, education, thought leadership, policy insights and business acumen.

The ABIS Central Team supports its Partners & Members by providing access to the network's expertise, commitment and resources. ABIS leverages these in collaborative projects and events that empower change and deliver impact.

Our Track Record

- Delivered 90+ knowledge development and learning initiatives
- Secured EUR 11+ million in EU grants to fund 60% of Corporate Responsibility research projects funded to date
- Invested EUR 2.5+ million in funding from ABIS' corporate founding partners and international foundations (UN Global Compact, Templeton, Roosevelt)
- Co-creator and Steering Committee member of the UN Global Compact Principles for Responsible Management Education (PRME)
- Co-developed with EFMD the Corporate Responsibility and ethics-related criteria in EQUIS, the world's leading business school accreditation standard

Our Story

ABIS (formerly known as EABIS) was founded in 2001 and launched at INSEAD in 2002 with the support of the leading Business Schools in Europe (INSEAD, IMD, London, ESADE, IESE, Copenhagen, Warwick, Vlerick, Ashridge, Cranfield and SDA Bocconi) in partnership with IBM, Microsoft, Johnson & Johnson, Unilever and Shell.

This initiative was driven by a shared belief that challenges linked to globalisation and sustainable development required new management skills, mindsets & capabilities. In order to respond to this need and to support research to underpin better education and learning, ABIS developed a stronger role in the arena.

Our Mission

Our mission is to build bridges and strengthen collaboration between the corporate and academic worlds to accelerate systematic change in business education and practice.

We create platforms and innovation spaces which enable our members to co-develop new knowledge, as well as education and learning frameworks, that will enhance the business contribution to society.

Message from the President

Dear ABIS Partners and Members,

It is a great pleasure for me to share with you the ABIS Highlights Report 2014-15.

The past months have been the starting point for a transformational change within ABIS and its network. As we are now entering a new phase that demands a better bridging between academia and business, we are refocusing the core mission of our organisation. Henceforth, ABIS will serve as a leading platform to enhance the co-development of knowledge as well as advancing education and learning frameworks that shall ultimately serve as the roots for a more robust contribution from business to and in society.

Further, ABIS is committed to enlivening its network by creating spaces and providing unique opportunities to its Partners & Members to advance their practice in education and business.

To achieve our future goals with our network, it also meant that a lot of work had to be done by the ABIS Secretariat in Brussels under the lead of its Managing Director, Joris-Johann Lenssen. The team put a great effort into the change of strategic outlook and the formation of new initiatives. All this may have been unseen to our Partners & Members, but I believe without a

doubt that those benefits will soon become apparent to everyone within the network.

In this regard, I would also like to thank our Board of Directors, who have stayed active and supportive to accompany the transformational shift of our organisation whilst encouraging ABIS to remain ambitious in its long term goals.

Finally, I would like to point out that the election of Doug Baillie, Chief Human Resources Officer of Unilever as the Chair of the Advisory Board of ABIS was a very important event. His expertise and visionary outlook into the future of talent development are a true enrichment to establishing a framework of how business education and research can accelerate progress towards a more sustainable future.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Alfons Sauquet Rovira'.

Prof. Alfons Sauquet Rovira

President, ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society

Global Dean, ESADE

Message from the Managing Director

Dear ABIS Partners and Members,

ABIS is at an important juncture in its development having established itself as an important player in the field of Business in Society. The founding model of corporate-academic partnership focused on knowledge creation and translation into education is perhaps even more relevant than when ABIS was founded.

For that reason we have renewed our founding mission to place even greater emphasis on the bridging between the worlds of academia and business. We want ABIS to become the platform for the acceleration of systemic change within business education and practice in the next few years.

As part of this transformation, a new internal structure is vital, as well as a clear positioning within the international landscape and new capabilities which increase our relevance and impact while delivering tangible value to our network. Many seeds have been planted to this effect within the past year, the benefits of which will become tangible in the coming months.

First among these is the development and implementation of a new platform that will help our Members to profit from the network experience. That is why we have established the Knowledge into Action Platform as a year-round process

grounded in the core principles of synergies between Members, network collaboration, and opportunity identification. It is supported by a twinned model of virtual and physical meeting spaces which empower our Members to champion new thinking and partnerships. At the heart of this process is our now annual Knowledge Into Action Forum, which took place for the first time this year and shall continue to be the arena for our Members to share their insights and projects with the rest of the network.

A desire to empower the network has also been the main driver for the development of our exclusive Members Area which includes a directory of both institutional and individual profiles, not to mention an extensive library of documents, literature, grant proposals and more. These profiles will allow us – but also the network itself – to connect more dynamically and effectively with fellow Members and potential collaboration partners than in the past.

We are committed to a better understanding of each Member's interests and quality of experience within the network. An annual membership survey is under development, which will give us far more structured feedback on how best to respond to and address your current and future agendas.

Last but not least, I would like to extend special thanks to the ABIS central team for all the dedicated work and support they have invested in this transition process, and above all their ongoing passion for this organisation.

Joris-Johann Lenssen

Managing Director, ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society

13th ABIS Annual Colloquium 2014

Transforming Tomorrow

With the 13th ABIS Annual Colloquium being our key event of the year, the Colloquium in 2014 focused on “Transforming Tomorrow: Leadership for a Sustainable Future”.

Throughout the two days, participants delved into the vital challenges faced by companies in leading change in their wider context. They explored the innovations being developed to transform systems, organisations and individuals in line with global sustainability imperatives.

The 2014 Colloquium was another milestone in the history of ABIS and fulfilled the objective of shaping a new learning, talent and knowledge development agenda in this vital area. The event attracted contributions of highest quality from senior figures in global business, academia, and international platforms from all over the world.

Challenges of Tomorrow

One of the critical issues that companies face is to ensure that their future leaders will possess the competencies and skills to guarantee their organisation’s future viability in a turbulent business context. Hence, sustainability needs to be deeply integrated into corporate HR/L&D frameworks as well as mainstream business school programmes and executive education.

Against this backdrop, the ABIS Annual Colloquium strived to convene a range of challenging dialogues to:

- Understand how companies can positively influence the systems in which they operate, and
- Bridge internal capability gaps and partner with business schools to develop the sustainability leaders of tomorrow who are central to the transformation of organisations and society.

Therefore, the 13th ABIS Annual Colloquium brought about a deep and reflective debate across traditional boundaries about the future sustainability-linked skills, knowledge and competences of universal relevance to business.

In order to facilitate the necessary shift in corporate strategy, it is of high relevance to leverage and catalyse change in business schools worldwide.

This crucial need for bridging between the corporate and academic worlds is what ultimately makes ABIS unique as a platform. Leading to lasting change in the way business and its leaders operate in the larger context of society.

Insights from the Colloquium

When discussing the business challenges in leading change, participants concentrated on the necessary capacities of individuals and organisations to undergo through such transformational change.

Further, the conference examined the current status of readiness of business schools to meet the rapidly evolving corporate agenda to increase their relevance and impact in the upcoming years. The contributions of the Colloquium 2014 were manifold, providing the latest insights from senior figures in global business practice and academia. The same holds true for the academic contributions to the conference, which have been published in a proceeding, consolidated file that is available on the ABIS website.

List of Selected Speakers

Doug Baillie
Chief HR Officer, *Unilever*

Jeremy Basset
Global Marketing Strategy
Director, *Unilever*

Xiang Bing
Dean, *Cheung Kong Graduate
School of Business*

CB Bhattacharya
Professor of Marketing, *E.ON
Chair in Corporate
Responsibility*, Dean of
International Relations, *ESMT*

Nancy Bocken
Lead researcher sustainable
business development,
*Institute of Manufacturing,
University of Cambridge*

Trevor Davis
Distinguished Engineer &
Consumer Products Expert,
IBM

John Elkington
Co-Founder & Executive
Chairman, *Volans*

Ian Ellison
Sustainability manager,
Jaguar Land Rover

Jack Frost
Director, *Johnson Matthey Fuel
Cells*

Jane Griffiths
Company Group Chairman,
Janssen Pharmaceuticals

Theo Hacking
Director, Graduate
Programmes, *University of
Cambridge Programme -
Sustainability Leadership*

Jules Hayward
Education Programme Lead,
Ellen MacArthur Foundation

Rodney Irwin
Managing Director, *WBCSD*

Peter Lacy
Managing Director, *Accenture
Strategy Practice & Accenture
Sustainability Services - Asia
Pacific*

Geoff McDonald
Director, *Bridge Partnership*

Sir Mark Moody-Stuart
Chairman, *Hermes Equity
Ownership Services*

George Njenga
Dean, *Strathmore Business
School, Nairobi*

Michael Skapinker
Associate Editor and Business
and Society Columnist,
Financial Times

Della Bradshaw
Business Education Editor
Financial Times

David Pencheon
Director, *Sustainable
Development Unit, NHS
England and Public Health
England*

ABIS Doctoral Summer School 2014 - Innovating for a Better World

Social Innovation

The ABIS Doctoral Summer School 2014 at Grenoble Ecole de Management focused on social innovation with a particular attention to exploring the ways in which innovation can serve to create better and more integrated social, environmental and economic business enterprises.

Social innovation implies an ability to create change that will enhance progress and sustainable human development. The Doctoral Summer Schools are part of ABIS's long standing commitment to support the development of the next generation of researchers around global business in society issues.

This includes:

- Institutional innovation regarding the structure and organisation of companies and their relationships with stakeholders;
- Innovative socially responsible and sustainable financing;
- Social innovation from bottom of pyramid situations in emerging economies and designed to foster socially sustainable inclusive development;
- The potential role of innovative clusters in promoting sustainable competitive development in whole regions;
- Innovation in the manner of measurement of company performance in CSR and sustainability;
- Innovation in the measurement of overall social performance of communities and states.

Tackling Central Societal Problems

At the Doctoral Summer School, social innovation was interpreted in the broadest sense to include not only such obvious examples as eco-friendly innovations which can enhance environmental sustainability but also any form of innovation which can help to create a better and more harmonious world. In particular, by tackling today's societal problems such as injustice in emerging economies, unemployment, inequalities, global climate change, ageing populations and access to healthcare.

Mentors at Doctoral Summer School 2014

Mark Esposito Grenoble Ecole de Management	Mollie Painter-Morland Nottingham Business School, Nottingham Trent University
Damon Golsorkhi Grenoble Ecole de Management	Patrick O'Sullivan Grenoble Ecole de Management
Amit Kapoor Institute of Competitiveness	Mark Smith Grenoble Ecole de Management
Bernard Leca Université Paris-Dauphine	

Dynamic Programme

The three-day Summer School provided a creative atmosphere for discussing innovative approaches to social innovation, corporate sustainability management, ecological innovation and ethics. Apart from that, our distinguished international researchers also provided insights into some of challenging areas related to the design and publication of research.

The Summer School programme incorporated three modes of exchange:

- **Group work** offered a forum for discussing the individual doctoral projects in small peer groups (2-4 people, depending on the topic), supported by the mentors;
- **Parallel sessions** focused on challenging areas of research: getting published, writing a paper-passed dissertation, etc.;
- **Plenary sessions** enabled presenting different perspectives on the conference theme, both academic and by invited practitioners.

Outcomes

The Summer School was linked to a special issue of the Journal of Management Development focusing on "Business and Sustainability: Innovating for a Better World".

The authors of the best contributions from the Summer School submitted their full papers to the journal which is still subject to the normal reviewing process, but is expected to be published by the end of January next year.

ABIS Knowledge Into Action Platform

Empowerment of Business-Academic Collaboration

ABIS is committed to putting engaged business-academic collaboration at the heart of everything we do. It is our aim to become more inclusive and demonstrate the value of ABIS as an innovation and collaboration hub for our Members in different parts of the world. In this regard, we aim that the network takes ownership to bring forward their initiatives.

In this regard, we have established a Knowledge Into Action Platform with three objectives in mind:

1. To enable our Partners & Members to gain deeper insights into a wide range of new funding opportunities – not least at EU level – directly from the people responsible for overseeing them;
2. To build an online Members Area, where Members can connect their interests, establish new relationships, and start working together – with the Secretariat's support – to submit excellent bids;
3. And to create an annual event at which all of our Members are empowered to showcase their latest 'big ideas' which may be leveraged into competitive grant proposals or other joint initiatives.

Year-round Engagement Process

ABIS Members Area

The ABIS Members Area is the new digital approach that has been developed to reach out to academic and corporate Members and connect them with each other. Now, Members can dive into the world of knowledge, tools, resources and connections to enable themselves and their organisations to drive impactful change. We strongly believe that the Members Area will bring our global network closer together and support you in our shared journey towards a better and more responsible future. This online platform will provide you with a relevant and useful content for engagement, as well as the opportunity to connect with every individual that is part of our ABIS network.

Our new online support system drives the Knowledge Into Action Platform in four essential ways:

1. It hosts individual profiles of hundreds of managers and scholars in ABIS' Member institutions, whose expertise is highlighted through a comprehensive tagging system – enabling Members to find and connect directly with colleagues in business and academia in areas of common interest;
2. The Members Area also contains functionalities to allow Members to post ideas or requests partners to develop new collaborative activities – be they funding proposals, round table dialogues, or other. Thanks to the tagging system, all Members with a stated interest in the main theme are automatically notified of new documents being posted or conversation threads opened.

3. As and when Members wish to develop their ideas into a more structured project or proposal, the Members Area offers closed, secure spaces for partnering institutions to store and archive key documents, knowledge, data and publications.
4. A year-round notification service informs Members of new funding and resourcing opportunities linked to their areas of interest. Overall, this is administered by the ABIS Secretariat, but Members can of course share new opportunities that they have identified with the network, to scope interest in collaboration. This again serves as an open loop system: Members can be inspired to work together when new resourcing channels are announced, or develop multi-actor partnerships before looking for new opportunities for additional resources.

ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum

In addition to our Members Area, we do not want to disregard the importance and effectiveness of our physical meetings. In this regard, we will annually host an event in Brussels, named the ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum.

The forum is the main physical meeting point for the network to come together and discuss new ideas for collaboration at different stages of development. An interactive format allows for Members to engage at three main levels:

1. A defined initiative for which the project leaders are seeking key expertise and capabilities to address specific gaps and/or optimise the competitiveness of a grant proposal;
2. An emerging initiative for which the champions wish to test different approaches and potential resource pathways before designing concrete project plans;
3. Frontier thinking for which the pioneers want to have exploratory discussions around new concepts and ideas, and to gauge network interest in developing them further.

It should be underlined, however, that the Members Area exists to allow Members to connect with each other at each level throughout the year! In this way, the Forum is a valuable milestone: it is a focal point around which Members can design their (virtual) planning and project development, but it is also the potential catalyst for new partnerships which can then be developed ex post through the Members Area.

Support by ABIS Projects Team

As the development of projects and proposals can be quite challenging, the ABIS Secretariat has a dedicated team in Brussels to support Members in a range of ways, such as the scheduling and hosting of consortia meetings online or offline.

As consortia move into the more structured phases of proposal development, ABIS can also provide an independent facilitator to chair your meetings, knowledgeable in the fundamental criteria for European Union funding, leaving Members free to concentrate on the conceptual and intellectual dimensions of proposal design.

Proposal Submission

Once a proposal is close to being submitted and the right funding scheme is targeted, ABIS will provide you support in the final submission of your work.

Of all the requirements in a proposal this can create the highest barriers, with organisations often having neither the budget, capacities nor the expertise to deliver a one-off competitive and comprehensive dissemination strategy.

ABIS offers an end-to-end submission service. We understands the unique issues associated with the global communication of scientific and technological research and are able to deliver a solution that is completely tailored to your individual needs.

ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum 2015

New Knowledge, Approaches and Ideas

As part of the process to turn the great knowledge of our network into action, 2015 was the first year that we convened an event that shall be the face of this very process.

The Knowledge Into Action Forum 2015 was the first step to tap into the rich pool of talent, new knowledge, approaches, and ideas that is the ABIS network. ABIS paved the way for future ground-breaking projects, led and mainly composed by ABIS Members.

Event Activities

On 28-29 April 2015, the Knowledge Into Action Forum took place at one of the ABIS Partner's premises: Vlerick Business School, Brussels Campus.

As it was the first edition, the first aim was to prepare participants to compete in the ever-changing arena of EU funding.

The amount of attendees and the quality of workshops championed had been outstanding, leading to interesting dialogues and debates, which were the source for continuous and fruitful collaboration.

The programme was divided into two distinct parts. During the first afternoon, attendees heard from the EU Commission and Project Coordinators about emerging priorities and themes linked to business in society and sustainability, as well as in-depth information about processes, key success criteria, impact expectations and experiences from on-going projects.

On the second day, we structured a range of small-scale workshops, led by corporate and academic Members around their own proposed themes. These were designed to connect and empower small clusters of Partners & Members to develop joint proposals for funding and wider collaboration in the months that follow.

Save the Date: ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum 2016 on 27-28 April in Brussels

Event Proceedings

As a follow-up to the event, a number of workshop proposals are now in the process of further development. Given the various stages these proposals are in, some are already under work for submission with different consortium partners involved.

It is our further, joint ambition to put forward more proposals in the years to come and to make the Knowledge Into Action Forum our yearly meeting point to discuss the joint projects our Members are developing.

List of Workshops

WS 1: The American University in Cairo – School of Business

Corporate Sustainability from a Comparative Lens – Europe, Middle East, North and South Africa

WS 2: Accenture

Circular Economy & Competitiveness

WS 3: BI Norwegian Business School

Building a network of members to explore corporate sustainability at Board level

WS 4: Comillas Pontifical University

Lifelong learning for young adults: better policies for growth and inclusion in Europe

WS 5: Mazars LLP

Long-termism in business – does it really pay?

WS 6: Amsterdam Business School

Transforming Data into Responsible Action: How to Improve Sustainable Value Chain Performance through Business Analytics

WS 7: ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society

The Alliance for business in society

WS 8: Kingston Business School

SME Business Model Innovation

WS 9: GIBS – Gordon Institute of Business Science, University of Pretoria

The Network for Business Sustainability: Bridging the gap between academic research and business sustainability challenges

WS 10: Mazars LLP

Tone at the Top – making it live throughout an organisation

WS 11: University of Koblenz-Landau

Entrepreneurship and Society in Europe

WS 12: Copenhagen Business School EDHEC Business School

Business and Human Rights: Unfolding the emerging regime to management professionals with an emphasis on the implications of the UN Guiding Principles on Business & Human Rights

EU-InnovatE

Background

ABIS is engaged together with 14 leading institutions in EU-InnovatE, one of the world's largest social science research projects linked to sustainable development. Supported by EUR 4.7 million in EU funding, it brings together a group of 40 researchers from nine different countries to investigate the role end users play in driving innovation and entrepreneurship in sustainable products and services.

Scope of the Project

From green electricity tariffs to car sharing schemes, many sustainable products and services have been brought to market by enthusiastic start-ups. More users and consumers than ever are turning their hands to business in a bid to solve social and environmental problems. ABIS with its fourteen collaborating European research institutes is investigating this trend to see what potential it holds for a sustainable economy. The project is also looking at how established companies engage end users in the development of sustainable products.

EU-InnovatE Benefits to Business and Society

A central thesis is that over time, end users and user entrepreneurs will play an essential role as innovation drivers in the transition to sustainable energy, food, living and mobility. Our scientific investigation provides new insights, evidence, tools and models around two major concepts: first, the role of end users and user entrepreneurs in sustainability innovation processes; and second the long-term opportunities and obstacles for company-driven and user-driven sustainability innovations to enhance sustainable lifestyles and green economy.

The project will deliver new understanding to companies on the potential of users to support corporate innovation design and processes. In parallel, it will empower policy-makers to become co-creators in advancing user sustainability entrepreneurship in Europe.

How to Engage

EU-InnovatE features dynamic platforms through which key societal stakeholders can share their knowledge, exchange experiences, and jointly shape pathways towards sustainable lifestyles. These include:

- Annual User Sustainability Innovation and Entrepreneurship Award;
- Laboratory experiments on new leadership and financing models;
- Policy innovation workshops;
- Summer Schools;
- Sustainable Futures design and simulation.

Progress to Date

- 17 company case studies have been implemented
- 15 entrepreneurial projects analysed and awarded
- Coalition with SEA for the Sustainable Entrepreneurship Award
- Launch of two summer school academies
- More than 5 academic articles published

Sustainable Entrepreneurship Award

For the year 2015, EU-InnovatE is delighted to confirm a new strategic partnership with future4you GmbH, the founders and organisers of the prestigious Sustainable Entrepreneurship Award (SEA) scheme.

The SEA was established in 2012 and annually presents awards to enterprises, projects and ideas which address a social or ecological problem by combining innovative solutions with a profitable commercial strategy. More than 1,000 submissions have been received since its launch.

This year's Sustainable Entrepreneurship Award will take place in Vienna on 12 November 2015.

ABIS Members involved

TUM - School of Management	Forum for the Future
Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt	Kozminski University
Copenhagen Business School	Politecnico di Milano
Cranfield University	University of Amsterdam
ESADE	

Key Links

www.euinnovate.com

www.se-award.org

www.forumforthefuture.org

Alliance for Advancing Health Assets

Health Improvement through Societal Change

In 2010, ABIS cofounded together with the Johnson & Johnson Corporate Citizenship Trust and Rutgers University the Advancing Health Alliance (AHA). The Alliance is a highly diverse global network of passionate individuals and organisations who are transforming society's approach to health improvement through social change. Since 2010, we have brought together leaders from across the global health spectrum for a "voyage of discovery" to identify concepts, models, processes and tools in support of informed decision making that could lead to better health in individuals, communities and systems.

The Advancing Health Alliance suggests not only to rethink the way health is perceived, resourced and managed but also uses the collective reach of its participants to research, implement and pressure test new tools allowing health practitioners, communities and policy-makers to collect evidence and advocate for a shift towards seeing health as an asset.

Current Status

Following a period of strategic consultation and reflection, the Alliance has entered its next phase. Since 2014 it has been engaged in co-investigating potential scenarios and in assessing impacts to reach a consensus on how we articulate our identity and operationalise the short and long term strategy. With a strengthened identity and a growth strategy the project is ready to embark in a new phase of expansion focusing on asset-based approaches to health.

Our Objectives

The Alliance's aim is to challenge and mobilise individuals and communities, as well as governmental and societal partners, to embrace asset-based approaches in both thinking and practice. Our health asset coalition goals include the following:

- Identifying and fostering decision making practices that empower individuals, communities, and health systems to build, own and manage their Health Assets (HA);
- Convening existing networks, and creating new partnerships to deploy resources for the mobilisation of Health Asset thinking, research, education and practice;
- Constructing and exchanging HA knowledge for the promotion of positive health and well-being.

Progress to Date

To meet these objectives, we have leveraged our collective intelligence to articulate our identity and generate new knowledge on asset based approaches in health. Collectively, we aim to launch several activities to enable systemic change through the adoption of asset based approaches in health. The Alliance on Advancing Health Assets is dedicated to:

- Influencing HA capacity building and health system strengthening by increasing HA thinking/acting and linking HA science to practice through the launch of a summer school;
- Enabling systemic change and developing tangible evidence showing the value of applying HA development approaches;
- Catalysing global networking, bridging across disciplines, and engaging in collaborative virtual Health Assets projects;
- Populating a virtual health assets knowledge repository with outputs from the programme;
- Broadcasting Health Assets success stories and their impacts.

- Opportunities to continue influencing, mobilising and supporting innovators.

Next Steps

Accordingly, during the next months we expect to continue to focus on:

- The strategic direction of the coalition in Q1/Q2 2016 reaching out to new partners and contributors;
- Organisation of a summer school;
- The set up of a knowledge repository drawing upon past and current research in the field of asset based approaches;
- Publication of an academic research around asset-based approaches in health;
- Continuing to enrich the network bringing on board new contributors and innovators.

Johnson & Johnson
**CORPORATE
CITIZENSHIP
TRUST**

Managing the Responsible Business Challenge in Africa

Corporate-Academic Partnership Programme

Africa's flourishing economies show the strength of entrepreneurship, innovation and talent. But how can this growth take into consideration the responsibility that goes with it, that talent is prepared for the leadership roles required to direct this growth and that the continent makes progress towards market stability and sustainable development?

Business-Academic Collaboration as a Catalyst

Business-academic collaboration has been identified as a catalyst that can develop cross-cutting competencies in general management and leadership, which has proven to facilitate integrated sustainability in different contexts. This requires sustained efforts in equipping faculty within African business schools and universities with the content, skills and networks in designing leadership development programmes with a focus on sustainability and ethics.

ABIS as a global network of businesses and academic collaboration has developed a new platform that aims to support responsible management education and leadership development for Africa's leaders from local companies, Government and NGOs.

Our initial priority is to develop the curriculum and delivery modes for an executive development programme, in collaboration with African academics, focused on leaders in Africa, enabling them to address the most pressing systemic problems within their context and foster stability. This collaborative cross-sectoral platform ultimately aims to contribute via executive education to the enhanced stability and development of markets, enterprises and communities.

Key Objectives

1. Designing core components of executive, management and small business development courses on responsible leadership across the African continent;
2. Developing faculty to support the delivery of responsible management education and leadership education for sustainability;
3. Designing and delivering new innovations in management at business schools as part of executive education offerings and through in company workshops.

Achievements in 2014/15

During 2014/2015, the ABIS Africa business-academic platform gathered through a series of workshops and worked together towards the common goal of designing a pilot course on leadership for Managing the Responsible Business Challenge in Africa. To define the building blocks of this pilot course, the platform has been focusing on:

1. Sharing current best practice models for leadership and management development in ethics and sustainability;
2. Facilitating strategic debate around the current gaps in leadership and management education towards sustainable and ethical business in Africa;
3. Designing core components, innovative methods and delivery structures of executive, management and small business leadership courses across the African continent.

In alignment with the fundamental purpose of transforming responsible leadership in Africa, with a new curriculum design for executive programmes, a first pilot model of the course has been co-created and conceptualised, as depicted in the Pilot Course Model.

The success of the course rests on the adoption of a cross-sectoral approach, integrated from its design phase to the delivery mode and feeding back into the public discourse.

The specific impact being targeted with this first pilot is to address the macro issue of responsible and ethical management and discuss the role of leadership in dealing with this systemic problem.

Pilot Course Model

Future Outlook

During the autumn of 2015 a number of faculty and corporate champions will undergo a train-the-trainer programme, which will lead to the first pilot early in 2016.

The course will prioritise on new approaches to curriculum design and faculty development to enable piloting and refining of training & learning innovations with middle and senior managers and executives. This first session will bring on board new stakeholders and set the path for future courses.

Innovation For Sustainability (I4S)

About I4S

Funded by the EU scheme titled 'People Marie Curie Actions', the Research and Competence Training Network for Sustainability-Driven Innovation (or simply I4S) aims at preparing early-stage researchers to generate and disseminate knowledge about how businesses and their managers contribute to, and participate in innovation that promotes economic, social development in ways that are environmentally sustainable.

The I4S project runs from January 1st 2013 until the end of December 2016 with 8 associated multinational corporate partners. Its network includes eight business schools, universities, and associate partners with prior research experience in aspects of sustainability, business and innovation. The training network is designed to expose early-stage researchers to a diversity of conceptual and empirical perspectives from which our understanding of sustainability-driven innovation can be improved. It brings together experienced university and business school faculty with an interest in developing new orientations to research by studying

areas that are relevant to sustainability-driven innovation, yet remain relatively under-theorised.

Eight early-stage researchers (ESRs) within I4S are now embarked on field work in different empirical settings: multinational enterprises in construction and retail, a medium-sized enterprise in electrical engineering; service providers (IT solutions, management consulting and social business innovation), a cross-sectorial enterprise association dedicated to sustainable development and a world-leading environmental NGO with global sustainability perspectives and reach.

Sustainability-driven Innovation

The members of the I4S consortium recognise ‘sustainability-driven innovation’ as a complex challenge that business scholars and practitioners ought to understand through interdisciplinary and trans disciplinary research rooted in a multi-level theory and research design. The long-held view of business organisations as insular entities which stand apart from society and innovate only to achieve instrumental interests is increasingly contested.

Some scholars pursuing research in the area of the business contribution to sustainable development support an alternative view of firms as systemic entities, able to develop connections with other actors in society, through multiple institutional frameworks, and working across sectors with communities and other social agents.

One proposition within this view is that sustainability-oriented corporations are seen to engage in innovation in a proactive, stakeholder-engaging way, and at multiple levels. This might involve technological innovation, innovation in business models or innovations that result in systems change. The realisation of ambitions of this kind invariably involves businesses and others in managerial and organisational innovation.

Training Network Activities

The activity of the 8 early-stage researchers is supported by training events carried out within the network. To date, this has resulted in the following activities:

1st Training Workshop (Brussels)

The focus of this workshop was to introduce the early stage researchers and other network members to the understandings and experiences of sustainability-driven innovation from the work of the non-academic partners. This will have a strong pan-European and beyond Europe dimension. The purpose was partly to understand how sustainability can be seen in different contexts.

1st Conference (Manchester)

The first Network Conference involved all the ESRs presenting their research statements and proposals, including research protocols. Feedback was given by ESRs and other network members as a way to improve their proposals.

1st Summer School (Nyenrode)

ESRs presented findings from their pilot studies and were asked to identify and discuss any methodological issues as they move from their pilot research to develop their empirical methods. Participants were given guidance on the research process from developing funding applications and the translation of scientific work into business accessible short publications.

2nd Training Workshop (Rotterdam)

This training workshop centred on the discussion of final theoretical and/or empirical dilemmas in the research protocols of all ESRs. ESRs were asked to share their concerns about academic careers and publishing and to check own progress in their programmes.

3rd Training Workshop (Gent)

The focus of this training workshop was on the translation of research into educational materials suitable for management students. ESRs presented short mock-up classes on their research and encouraged to provide feedback and group support on teaching approaches and skills.

ABIS Members involved

Copenhagen Business School	Nyenrode Business Universiteit
University of Exeter Business School	Vlerick Business School
Manchester Business School	Leuphana University, Centre for Sustainability Management
Rotterdam School of Management, Erasmus University	University of Cape Town

ABIS Thought Leadership Round Tables

High-Level Corporate-led Debates on Cross-Sector Strategic Issues

In late 2013, ABIS developed a standard format for Thought Leadership Round Tables, designed to provide the maximum interaction and benefit to all participants. Attendees are selected to provide a mix of academic and corporate backgrounds, with each person contributing their own experience in the specific topic.

In 2014, ABIS supported three Thought Leadership Round Tables. These indulged high-level debates on cross-sectorial strategic issues, supported by C-suite speakers and international academic experts. The 2014 series focused on 3 distinct themes, championed by ABIS Member companies: *Leadership and Technology*, *Management Tools for Sustainable Assessment* and *Sustainable Portfolio Management*.

Leadership and Technology - TATA Communications

ABIS and Tata Communications hosted a ground breaking round table spread across 8 cities worldwide using TATA Communications' global telepresence rooms to discuss the impact of technology on leadership and sustainability.

Technological advancements within global organisations have created the possibility to manage international teams, utilise global supply chains, and reach international markets. The new opportunities that this global environment presents can only be meaningfully utilised if business leaders are skilled in various forms of stakeholder engagement, facilitated via diverse communication platforms. Leaders also have to understand the sustainability-related challenges that their organisations face. To interact with the various parts of their increasingly complex organisations and stakeholder networks, business leaders have come to employ a vast range of new communication technologies, including email, teleconferencing, telepresence rooms, websites, social media, blogs and other discussion forums.

Over 60 participants addressed a range of key discussion points, including:

- Leadership capacities for creating sustainable and ethical global organisations;
- Aligning leadership's messages between internal and external stakeholders;
- Dealing with the challenges of space and time: speed, time-zones etc.;
- Technology as key asset in managing leadership challenges in global organisations.

Management Tools For Sustainable Assessment - Candriam

A seminar was hosted by ABIS and Candriam Investors Group (formerly known as Dexia Asset Management) in Brussels for CSR officers and senior experts to discover a new sustainability assessment methodology offering rankings for companies within ten industry sectors. A sustainability assessment methodology has been developed over several years by Candriam in on-going dialogue with an independent Advisory Board including representatives of Vlerick Business School, University of Geneva and ABIS. The results deliver deep insight, an embedded approach and the possibility to change towards better performance of business in society.

At the round table discussions, participants learned about sustainability regarding the sector in which they operate (Macroanalysis) and the positioning of the sector in the megatrends. The participants discovered the sector's best practices in terms of stakeholder management (Microanalysis). The participants offered their feedback on Candriam methodology and some have planned to apply the criteria of the methodology in their own work.

Sustainable Portfolio Management - Solvay Group

ABIS supported the Solvay Group to host a workshop on its Sustainable Portfolio Management Methodology (SPM), a standard for the Group's sustainability assessments of its business portfolio.

The SPM tool is aimed at visualising the risks and opportunities associated with the sustainability megatrends so that appropriate strategic decisions can be taken to balance the portfolio on the sustainable perspective, this being along two main axes:

- The financial risks and opportunities linked to the environmental footprint of its manufacturing activities;
- The opportunities and risks from a market perspective, by materialising the extent to which customers and/or consumers acknowledge that a given product is eventually part of the solution they are seeking in order to address their own environmental concerns.

EU Horizon 2020 Engagement Opportunities

Biggest EU Research and Innovation Programme

Horizon 2020 is the largest EU Research and Innovation programme of all time with close to EUR 80 billion of funding available for a period of over 7 years (2014 to 2020). The programme aims to pave the way for more breakthroughs, discoveries and world-firsts by taking great ideas from science to the market.

By coupling research and innovation, Horizon 2020 is helping to achieve this with its emphasis on excellent science, industrial leadership and tackling societal challenges. The goal is to ensure Europe produces world-class science, removes barriers to innovation and makes it easier for the public and private sectors to work together in delivering innovation.

It seeks in part to strengthen the bridges and relationships between industry, academia and society, as well as international strategic partnerships with different regions in the world, so that Europe may more effectively pursue its strategic ambition of 'smart, sustainable, inclusive growth'. As a result, Horizon 2020 funding is structured around industrial leadership and tackling the societal challenges of our time.

Funding Proposal Development through ABIS

Monitoring the publication of the funding opportunities, calls and grants from all these diverse programmes, can be a time consuming and frustrating job.

The ABIS Secretariat provides shoulder-to-shoulder support for our Partners & Members, helping you to proceed the application from its inception and development to a successful submission. This proposal-building process will be further enhanced through our Members Area, which will, apart from finding the right consortium partners, also help you to target your proposals to the right funding opportunities.

Recent ABIS Submissions

During the past years, ABIS has helped its Partners & Members to put forward various Project Proposals under the Horizon 2020 funding scheme.

H2020 - 2014

Towards a Responsible Research and Innovation System (FoTRRIS)

ABIS Members involved:

- Central European University
- Manchester Business School

H2020 - 2015

CloudCraft

ABIS Members involved:

- TUM - School of Management

Yield To Youth

ABIS Members involved:

- ESADE
- Kozminski University
- Lappeenranta School of Technology
- Manchester Business School
- Nyenrode Business Universiteit
- The American University in Cairo

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions 2015

Innovative Training Network proposal: Research and Competence Training of Early-Stage Researchers in and for Sustainability-Oriented Enterprises (SustEIn)

ABIS Members involved:

- Accenture
- Cologne Business School
- Cranfield School of Management
- Grenoble Ecole de Management
- ISTUD
- Manchester Business School
- Nottingham Business School, Nottingham Trent University
- Rotterdam School of Management, Erasmus University
- University of Cape Town Graduate School of Business
- University of Koblenz-Landau, Central Institute for Scientific Entrepreneurship & International Transfer

Aligned Technology, Innovation, and Management for the Medicine of Tomorrow Redefining Healthcare Landscapes by Means of Holistic Competence Building (ATIMM)

ABIS Members involved:

- Johnson & Johnson
- MIP-Politecnico di Milano
- University of Edinburgh

ABIS Publications

Business & Professional Ethics Journal Vol. 33, No. 4, 2014 - ABIS Doctoral Summer School 2013

The Business and Professional Ethics Journal is a peer-reviewed forum for interdisciplinary research that explores the systemic causes of ethical challenges in business and professional life. The Journal provides an outlet for papers that make significant contributions to the development of alternative theories and practices within business and professional ethics, and that examine why global ethical issues, such as poverty alleviation and sustainability, emerge and persist.

Journal of Management Development Vol. 33, Issue 8/9, 2014

Beyond an exclusive orientation towards economic models, mathematical theories and management tools, management education is also supposed to cover aspects of personal purpose, development and sense-making of future managers. "Practical Wisdom for Sustainable Management" aims at overcoming the often decried normative void in management education.

During the first explorative phase of the project, ABIS, EFMD, and the Yale University for Faith and Culture initiated a series of conferences and Journal of Management Development Special Issues. These activities were supposed to shed light on the potential role of the major philosophical, spiritual and religious traditions for providing content for teaching Practical Wisdom in the Business school classroom.

In the years 2010-2013, the Journal of Management Development published special issues on the Christian, Chinese classical, Jewish, and Islamic Traditions.

For the year 2014, the journal finalised the series with its focus on Buddhist and Indian religious traditions.

Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society Vol. 14, Issue 5, 2014

The fundamental question that hangs over the finance and sustainability debate - and a question that emerges as one of the most challenging areas of interest for companies, investors, academics and policymakers - is how to finance the transition to a more sustainable global economy and society.

This special issue includes papers that frame and test the linkages between sustainability, finance and corporate governance. All included papers contributed to the overall challenge of how to finance the transition to a more sustainable global economy and society, by focusing on specific angles like the treatment of risks, inclusive decision-making and the functioning of markets.

Central And Eastern Europe Case Studies

Corporate responsibility has become an important topic in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) because of the region's increasing integration into the global political and economic system in recent decades. There is an emerging need to integrate corporate responsibility in the mainstream management education and executive education in CEE countries.

ABIS engaged a research team to identify and analyse the best corporate performers from parts of Central and Eastern Europe based on a specially tailored assessment tool. The aim was to prepare a collection of educational case studies. The research led to a total of 6 case studies from Hungary, Poland and the Ukraine involving the following ABIS Partners & Members:

- CEU Business School
- GlaxoSmithKline
- Kozminski University
- St. Petersburg University Graduate School of Management

ABIS Membership

New ABIS Partners and Members 2014-15

The following ABIS Members were ratified and accepted by the ABIS Board of Directors since the beginning of the year 2014.

New ABIS Partners

New ABIS Members

ABIS Partners

Corporate Partners

- EPPA
- GlaxoSmithKline
- IBM
- ING
- Johnson & Johnson
- Solvay SA
- Unilever

Academic Partners

- Ashridge Business School
- Copenhagen Business School
- Cranfield School of Management
- ESADE Business School
- IESE
- IMD
- INSEAD
- London Business School
- Manchester Business School
- Nottingham Business School, Nottingham Trent University
- Nyenrode Business University
- SDA Bocconi School of Management
- Vlerick Business School

ABIS Members

Corporate Members

- Accenture
- Candriam
- COFRA
- Intel
- Mazars
- Recticel
- TATA Communications
- Telecom Italia
- ESMT European School of Management and Technology
- European University Business School
- Gordon Institute for Business Science (GIBS)
- Grenoble Ecole de Management
- Henley Business School
- Hong Kong University of Science and Technology: HKUST
- Inha University Business School, College of Business Administration
- INSEEC
- ISCTE Business School
- ISM
- ISTUD
- Kent Business School
- Kingston University Business School
- Kozminski University
- Lappeenranta University of Technology
- Leuphana University, Centre for Sustainability Management
- Maastricht University
- Mannheim University
- MIP - Politecnico di Milano
- Plymouth University, Plymouth Business School
- Rotterdam School of Management, Erasmus University
- Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences
- Royal Holloway University of London, School of Management
- Rutgers University
- Solvay Business School
- St. Petersburg University - Graduate School of Management
- The American University in Cairo
- The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
- TIAS School for Business and Society
- TUM School of Management
- Turku School of Economics
- University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam Business School
- University of Bath School of Management University of Cape Town Graduate School of Business
- University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership
- University of Edinburgh Business School
- University of Exeter Business School
- University of Hull
- University of Koblenz-Landau, Central Institute for Scientific Entrepreneurship & International Transfer
- University of New South Wales CSI
- University of Stellenbosch Business School
- University of West England
- Waikato Management School
- Warsaw School of Economics

Academic Members

- Al Akhawayn University School of Business Administration
- ALTIS - University Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
- Asian Institute of Management
- Asian Institute of Technology
- Audencia Nantes
- Ben Gurion University of Negev
- BI Norwegian Business School
- Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt
- Central European University Business School
- Cologne Business School
- Comillas Pontifical University
- Coventry University
- Durham University Business School
- Ecole Hôtelière de Lausanne
- EDHEC Business School
- ESCP Europe

ABIS Membership

ABIS Affiliate Members

- AABS - Association of African Business Schools
- AccountAbility
- Agentur Mehrwert
- AIESEC
- Business & Society
- Business in the Community
- Business in the Community Ireland
- CEEMAN
- CSR Asia
- CSR Europe
- Drucker Society
- EFMD
- Foretica
- Forum for the Future
- Global Reporting Initiative
- Global Sustain
- InnoCSR
- Italian Centre for Social Responsibility
- Japan Forum of Business and Society
- Latin American Council of Management Schools (CLADEA)
- Net Impact
- Observatoire de la Responsabilité des Entreprises
- Sodalitas

Principles for Responsible Management Education (PRME)

PRME Principles for Responsible Management Education

Overview

The Principles for Responsible Management (PRME) was launched in 2007 as a United Nations Global Compact initiative. It aims to globally inspire and lead change in the field of responsible management and thought leadership.

Inspired by internationally accepted values, which include the UN Global Compact's Ten Principles, the Six Principles of PRME provide a structure for engagement in order to advance academic institutions in terms of social responsibility by incorporating universal values into curricula and research. By doing so, PRME seeks to establish a process of continuous enhancement among institutions of management education in order to develop a new generation of business leaders that is capable of managing the complex challenges faced by business and society in the 21st century.

Gradual and Systemic Change in Business Education

The PRME initiative aims to create a framework for gradual, systemic change in business schools and management-related institutions. This change is based on three distinctive characteristics of the initiative: continuing improvement, a learning network, and reporting progress to stakeholders. To report on progress of participating institutions to stakeholders through Sharing Information on Progress (SIP) reports is a crucial part of the active commitment to PRME.

Our Involvement

With ABIS being a co-creator of PRME, as well as member of its Steering Committee, we are part of the group of global and regional associations, which advise the PRME Secretariat on a wide range of strategic and operational issues. Furthermore, the 2014 Steering Committee meeting was chaired by our Director International Programmes, Simon Pickard.

The committee as a whole is committed to advance long-term goals in responsible management education in business schools world wide. Finally, ABIS also aims to align our own initiatives with UN policies around sustainable development through the partnership with PRME.

ABIS Board of Directors

Alfons Sauquet Rovira, ABIS
President and Chairman of the Board of Directors

Prof. Manuela Brusoni, SDA Bocconi
Professor of Public Management and Policy

Dr. Thomas Osburg, Intel
Director Europe Corporate Affairs and Innovation

Prof. Mark Esposito, Grenoble Ecole de Management
Professor of Business and Economics at Grenoble Ecole de Management and Harvard University's Division of Continuing Education

Prof. Esben Pedersen, Copenhagen Business School
Director of Centre for Corporate Social Responsibility

Adrie Heinsbroek, ING Belgium
Head of Sustainability

Dr. Stefan Schepers, EPPA
Partner

Prof. Andrew Kakabadse, Henley Business School
Professor of Governance and Leadership

Els Vandercandelaere, Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Johnson & Johnson Group
VP HR J&J Consumer North America

Jens Meyer, CEDEP
Director General and Dean of Programs

Prof. Luk Van Wassenhove, INSEAD
The Henry Ford Chaired Professor of Manufacturing

ABIS Team

Joris-Johann Lenssen,
Managing Director

Simon Pickard,
Director International
Programmes

Gordana Kierans,
Director Relationships
& Communication

Rúben Durães,
Manager Operations

Mollie Painter-Morland,
Project Director Africa
Initiative

Sam Lee,
Regional Director Asia

Ludwig Roger,
Manager EU Projects &
Funding

Elena Urizar,
Projects Manager

Varkey George,
Project Manager Africa

Mario Pansera,
Marie Skłodowska-
Curie Research Fellow &
Project Manager (I4S)

Fabian Martinez,
Marie Skłodowska-Curie
Research Fellow & Project
Manager (I4S)

Anna Ozolina,
Relationships
Coordinator

Ruth García Palafox,
Administrative
Coordinator

Marco Matriciano,
Projects Assistant

Patrick Niemann,
Communication
Assistant

Karolina Sobczak,
Events Assistant

